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The use of ICT globally

Has increased by 118.89% on average for the countries analyzed between 2013 and 2022.

The use of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) refers to the employment of digital technologies, tools, and systems that enable users to access, store, transmit, and manipulate information. This includes the use of computers, smartphones, the internet, software applications, and other digital devices and platforms for a wide range of purposes such as communication, data processing, education, business operations, and entertainment. In a broader context, the use of ICT includes activities such as browsing the internet, communicating via email and messaging, using software applications for tasks like word processing and creating presentations, online transactions such as e-commerce and banking, engaging in social media, using cloud computing for data storage and collaboration, as well as utilizing tools for remote work and digital learning. The use of ICT is fundamental in modern societies as it enhances efficiency, connectivity, and access to information across various sectors, including education, business, healthcare, and government. The available data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Global ICT usage in 2022. At the top of the rankings, Iceland, Denmark, and Switzerland emerge as global leaders in ICT adoption, with percentages of 89.1%, 88.5%, and 88.2%, respectively. These countries, known for their high standard of living and commitment to technological innovation, benefit from advanced digital infrastructures and an education system that prepares citizens for conscious and effective use of technology. The strong penetration of digital technologies in these countries can be attributed to a combination of favorable government policies, investments in the ICT sector (Information and Communication Technology), and a culture that embraces innovation. Following closely, South Korea, the United Kingdom, and Sweden also maintain high levels of technological adoption, with scores ranging between 87.4% and 86.5%. South Korea, in particular, is known for its ultra-fast internet network and widespread smartphone use, facilitating access to a wide range of digital services. The United Kingdom and Sweden, on the other hand, are distinguished by their strong digital economies, where technology plays a key role in economic development and job creation. In the mid-range of the rankings, countries like France (85.1%), Malta (84.3%), and the United States (84%) are found. The position of the United States might be surprising, considering the country's dominant role in the global technology sector. However, the percentage reflects the disparity in access to technology across different regions and population groups. In many cases, access to advanced technologies is concentrated in urban areas or among wealthier populations, leaving rural areas and disadvantaged communities behind. Other countries, such as Hong Kong (83%) and Saudi Arabia (82.9%), show strong technology penetration, albeit in very different contexts. Hong Kong, as a global financial and commercial hub, has developed a robust digital infrastructure that supports its economic activities. Saudi Arabia, on the other hand, reflects the effect of recent government policies aimed at economic diversification and reducing dependence on oil, with an increasing emphasis on innovation and technology adoption. The presence of countries like Estonia (82.2%) and Lithuania (80.4%) at the top of the rankings highlights how even smaller nations with limited resources can achieve significant results through targeted policies and strategic

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investments. Estonia, for example, is a pioneer in digital government adoption and the creation of a technology-based society, with digitized public services and an e-residency infrastructure that attracts entrepreneurs from around the world. At the bottom of the rankings, worrying situations are observed in countries like Yemen (11.5%), Myanmar (0%), and Niger (13%), where ICT adoption is extremely low. These figures reflect the economic and political difficulties these countries face, including civil wars, widespread poverty, and political instability, which prevent the development of the necessary infrastructure to support the spread of digital technologies. The lack of access to technology in these contexts can further exacerbate economic and social inequalities, creating a digital divide that is difficult to bridge. Another important aspect to consider is the case of Myanmar, which shows an adoption rate of 0%. This figure can be interpreted in light of recent political turmoil and government restrictions on internet and technology access. Authoritarian conditions and crackdowns on digital communication have drastically limited the ability of citizens to access technological resources, making the country an extreme case of digital exclusion. Another group of countries, including Brazil (62.9%), Argentina (62.2%), and India (45%), are positioned in the lower half of the rankings. Despite these countries having emerging economies and considerable growth potential in the technology sector, disparities in access to technology, especially in rural areas, remain a significant challenge. In Brazil, for instance, rapid urbanization and economic inequality have created a situation where access to technology is highly variable, with rural areas lagging behind urban ones. In India, despite progress in digitalization through government initiatives like Digital India, access to ICT is still limited due to factors such as inadequate infrastructure and digital illiteracy. The data also shows that in countries like Nigeria (31.3%), Kenya (32.6%), and Uganda (26.4%), technology adoption is still relatively low. However, it is important to note that these countries are making progress, albeit slowly, through initiatives aimed at improving access to technology and educating the population on its use. In many cases, the adoption of mobile technologies is helping to overcome some of the existing barriers, enabling broader access to digital services even in remote areas. The overall analysis of this data underscores the importance of targeted public policies and investments in technological infrastructure to promote ICT adoption. Countries that invest in digital education, network access, and technological innovation tend to show higher levels of adoption, which in turn support economic and social development. However, the disparity between countries and within them indicates that there is still much work to be done to ensure that the benefits of the digital revolution are equitably distributed across the globe. Access to ICT is not just a matter of economic development but also of social inclusion and equity, and requires continuous commitment from governments, businesses, and communities.

Global ICT usage between 2013 and 2022. Among the countries that have recorded the greatest progress in ICT adoption are Ethiopia, Cameroon, and Bangladesh, which have seen their indices increase by 29.2%, 36.3%, and 37.3% respectively between 2013 and 2022, with impressive percentage changes of 3650%, 3025%, and 2869.2%. These extraordinary numbers reflect a very low initial stage of technological development, with limited access to digital technologies in 2013, which allowed extremely high growth rates once technological infrastructures and government policies began to encourage widespread adoption. In these countries, the implementation of mobile technologies and low-cost internet access have played a crucial role in fostering growth. Ethiopia, for example, has benefited from significant expansion of its digital infrastructure, facilitated by increasing public and private investment. Similarly, countries like Mozambique, Zambia, and Niger have shown remarkable increases, with percentage changes of 2362.5%, 2209.1%, and 2066.7%, respectively. Despite these impressive growth percentages, the absolute levels of adoption remain relatively low, highlighting the fact that although significant progress has been made, these countries still have a large digital divide to bridge compared to more developed nations. Growth in these

contexts can be attributed to increased accessibility to mobile technologies and educational initiatives that have improved digital awareness and skills among the population. Countries like Nigeria, Nepal, and Guinea have also recorded notable progress, with percentage changes exceeding 1000%. Nigeria, in particular, has seen growth of 1741.2%, reflecting the expansion of internet penetration and mobile device use in one of Africa's largest economies. However, this exponential growth hides a complex reality: the digital divide within the country is still wide, with large segments of the rural population remaining excluded from the benefits of digitalization. The landscape of technology adoption varies greatly in middle-income countries. Uzbekistan and Cambodia have seen significant growth, 873.4% and 732.3% respectively, thanks to government policies that have promoted the expansion of digital networks and access to mobile devices. In these nations, technology has become a key element for economic and social development, with a growing number of people using digital tools for education, access to financial services, and communication. In Asia, countries like India, Indonesia, and Vietnam have also seen significant increases in ICT adoption, with India recording growth of 703.6% and Indonesia 425.5%. These countries, characterized by large populations and rapid urbanization rates, have seen an explosion in mobile technology use as the primary means of accessing the internet. In India, the "Digital India" initiative has contributed to expanding access to digital technologies, although significant challenges related to inequality in access still remain. In Africa, countries like Ghana, Burkina Faso, and Rwanda have shown strong growth rates in technology adoption, with Ghana seeing an increase of 1465.6%. These results reflect concerted efforts to expand telecommunications infrastructure and make digital services more accessible. However, the sustainability of this growth depends on the ability to address structural issues such as poverty, education, and access to electricity, which remain significant barriers in many regions. In Europe and the Americas, growth rates have generally been more moderate but no less significant. Countries like Latvia, Albania, and the Dominican Republic have recorded notable absolute changes, with Latvia seeing an increase of 49.7 percentage points. These countries have benefited from European digital cohesion policies and investments in improving their technological infrastructures. In Latin America, Paraguay and Brazil have shown significant growth, with increases of 298.4% and 180.8%, respectively, reflecting an expansion of digital connectivity and growing demand for online services. In the Middle East and North Africa, countries like Oman, Jordan, and Iran have also seen robust growth, with increases exceeding 150%. These countries have benefited from government programs aimed at modernizing digital infrastructures and promoting technological education, as well as from a significant young demographic that has quickly adopted new technologies. At the bottom of the rankings, however, are developed nations like Switzerland, Hong Kong, and Luxembourg, which have recorded lower percentage changes of 12.5%, 1.6%, and 6.3%, respectively. This data is hardly surprising: in these countries, ICT adoption was already very high in 2013, leaving little room for significant further increases. Here, technological innovations focus more on the quality and sophistication of digital services rather than on the expansion of basic access. Countries like the United Kingdom, Sweden, and Denmark have also shown moderate growth rates, with percentage changes below 30%. In these cases, too, these are nations that already enjoyed widespread digital technology adoption in 2013, and their growth is more a reflection of a refinement of existing capabilities than a radical expansion of access. These countries continue to lead in advanced technology and digital applications, contributing to the development of new global standards. Finally, it is interesting to note that even the United States and Japan, global leaders in the technology sector, have seen moderate increases of 56.1% and 32.9%, respectively. This suggests that despite their advanced technological ecosystems, growth in these countries has been limited by market saturation factors and the need to address issues such as cybersecurity and digital sector regulation. In conclusion, the data reveals a highly diversified global landscape in ICT adoption, with some countries recording exponential growth rates, while others show more contained growth due to

already high levels of adoption. The challenge for the coming years will be to bridge the existing digital divide, ensuring that the benefits of ICT are accessible to all populations, regardless of their geographic or socioeconomic context. Public policies, education, and investments in digital infrastructure will continue to play a crucial role in this process of technological globalization.

Economic policies. Increasing the use of ICT in a country requires a multidimensional approach that combines investments in digital infrastructure, tax incentives, educational policies, support for innovation, and favorable regulations. First, it is crucial to develop robust and accessible digital infrastructure. The government can initiate and support projects to expand high-speed broadband coverage, especially in rural and disadvantaged areas where internet access is often limited. A solid digital infrastructure not only facilitates access to online services but is also fundamental for the development of advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT). Additionally, the government can stimulate private investment in this sector through public-private partnerships (PPP), tax breaks for companies investing in digital infrastructure, and incentives for the adoption of green and sustainable technologies. At the same time, a broad effort in digital education is necessary. This can be done by introducing the teaching of digital skills at the school level, updating curricula to include subjects such as programming, cybersecurity, and digital literacy. The enhancement of digital skills should also extend to the workforce through professional training and retraining programs. The goal is to create a population not only capable of using ICT but also able to actively contribute to their development and application in various economic sectors. In this context, lifelong learning policies become essential to keep the workforce competitive and adaptable in an ever-evolving market. Another key component is support for innovation and entrepreneurship in the technology sector. The government can incentivize the creation and growth of tech startups through facilitated financing programs, business incubators and accelerators, and by simplifying regulations for new business creation. Access to capital is often a barrier for startups, so it is essential that public policies promote access to venture capital funds, crowdfunding, and other innovative forms of financing. Additionally, promoting innovation ecosystems, such as technology districts or science parks, can encourage collaboration between companies, universities, and research institutes, thus accelerating technology transfer and the commercialization of innovations. An equally important aspect concerns tax and incentive policies. Tax breaks for companies investing in ICT and digitalization can be a strong stimulus. For example, the government can introduce tax credits for research and development (R&D) in the technology sector or for companies adopting advanced digital solutions such as AI, automation, or cloud computing. These policies can be combined with incentives for purchasing hardware and software, or for adopting advanced cybersecurity systems, crucial for protecting digital infrastructures and sensitive data. In the context of digital transformation, industrial policies must also adapt. The digitalization of traditional industries, often referred to as "Industry 4.0," represents a great opportunity to improve the competitiveness and efficiency of businesses. The government can facilitate this process by offering technical and financial support to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) embarking on digitalization paths. This can include, for example, consultancy programs, specific training for the implementation of advanced technologies, and the creation of industrial competence networks that can serve as centers of excellence for the dissemination of best practices. Another crucial policy is the promotion of e-government, or the use of ICT to improve the efficiency and accessibility of public services. Digitizing government services not only makes state operations more efficient but also increases the population's familiarity with digital technologies, promoting more widespread use of these technologies. The introduction of digital platforms for services such as tax payments, business registration, or access to health services

can significantly reduce costs and time for citizens and businesses. Moreover, a well-functioning digital government can serve as a catalyst for the adoption of technologies by the private sector, creating a more transparent and competitive environment. Economic policies must also address regulatory challenges. A clear and favorable regulatory framework is essential to promote ICT adoption. This includes personal data protection, digital platform regulation, and support for fair competition in the digital market. Privacy protection and cybersecurity are central issues that need to be addressed through rigorous regulations that balance the need for innovation with the protection of user rights. At the same time, the government must avoid overly restrictive regulations that could stifle innovation or limit access to new technologies. Finally, economic policies to increase ICT use must also consider the international dimension. In an increasingly globalized world, international cooperation in technology and innovation is crucial. Governments must work together to harmonize technological standards, facilitate digital trade, and promote cross-border collaboration in research and development. Actively participating in international initiatives, such as those promoted by the European Union, the United Nations, or the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), can provide countries with access to resources, knowledge, and global markets, thus facilitating the integration of ICT at the national level. In conclusion, increasing the use of ICT requires a holistic approach that combines infrastructure investments, digital education, tax incentives, support for innovation, favorable regulations, and international cooperation. These policies must be carefully coordinated and implemented to ensure that all segments of the population have access to the opportunities offered by digital technologies. Only in this way will it be possible to create an inclusive, innovative, and resilient technological ecosystem capable of addressing future challenges and promoting sustainable economic development.

Conclusions. The average value of ICT service usage grew between 2013 and 2022 by 118.89%, rising from a value of 27.56 to a value of 60.34. However, there are a number of countries where the value of ICT service usage has grown significantly, much more than the average, namely: Ethiopia with +3650.0%, Cameroon with +3025%, Bangladesh with +2869.20%, Mozambique with +2362.50%, Zambia with +2200.10%. There are other countries where this value has grown less than the average, namely Switzerland with a value of +12.50%, Germany with +9.30%, Singapore with +8.10%, Luxembourg with +6.30%, Hong Kong with +1.60%.

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